

HEPATOPROTECTIVE POTENTIAL OF SAFFLOWER OIL COMPARED TO COTTONSEED OIL

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Relevance: Toxic hepatitis is accompanied by profound hepatocellular damage and impairment of vital metabolic processes. One of the main markers of hepatocyte destruction is the elevation of cytolytic enzymes, particularly alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST) [3,6]. Pharmacological hepatoprotectors are effective but often associated with side effects and limited accessibility in long-term use [1, 4]. Natural oils with bioactive components represent a promising alternative to restore liver function. Safflower oil has been noted for its hepatoprotective properties, but comparative studies with other vegetable oils remain insufficient [2, 5]. Clarifying these effects is important for integrating dietary oils into hepatology practice.

Aim of the study: To compare the hepatoprotective effects of safflower and cottonseed oils in rats with experimental toxic hepatitis.

Materials and Methods: The experiment included 40 male rats divided into intact, control, safflower oil, and cottonseed oil groups (n=5 each). Acute toxic hepatitis was modeled by high-dose paracetamol administration. From day 3, rats received safflower or cottonseed oil at 10 ml/kg for 14 days. Serum ALT, AST, and alkaline phosphatase were measured using biochemical assay kits (Cypress Diagnostics, Belgium). Statistical analysis used Student's t-test with significance at $p < 0.05$.

Results: In control rats with toxic hepatitis, ALT and AST levels increased 1.22–1.35-fold compared to intact animals, reflecting significant hepatocellular injury. Safflower oil reduced ALT by 1.17 times relative to control, whereas cottonseed oil did not significantly affect ALT activity. AST levels decreased 1.48-fold in the safflower oil group compared to control, while only 1.23-fold in the cottonseed oil group ($p < 0.05$). Alkaline phosphatase, elevated 1.43 times in the control group, normalized under safflower oil treatment, whereas cottonseed oil further increased it by 1.12 times relative to control ($p < 0.05$). γ -Glutamyl transferase activity showed a marked decline under safflower oil compared to cottonseed oil. These results confirm that safflower oil more effectively restores liver enzyme activity and reduces cytolytic processes.

Conclusions: Safflower oil demonstrated stronger hepatoprotective activity than cottonseed oil in experimental toxic hepatitis. It provided significant reduction in ALT and AST, normalization of alkaline phosphatase, and stabilization of GGT activity. Cottonseed oil showed limited protective potential and even adverse effects on certain enzymes. The hepatoprotective properties of safflower oil support its role as a functional dietary supplement for liver protection. Future clinical studies should validate these experimental results in human pathology.

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